

A Review Nutritional prospects of wheatgrass and natures finest Medicine

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ABSTRACT:

Nutraceuticals are organic and traditional foods consumed nowadays to maintain a healthy lifestyle and get rid of lifestyle diseases like obesity, cancer, diabetes, hypertension, etc. Globally, herbal products have become increasingly popular in recent years. Wheatgrass (*Triticum aestivum*) is a nutraceutical proven to be a dietary supplement and beneficial for cancer-suffering patients. Wheatgrass possesses many beneficial antioxidant properties: anti-cancer activity, anti-bacterial activity, anti-fungal activity, and anti-microbial activity. Due to the presence of resistant starch, lignans, phenolic acids, alkylresorcinols, and numerous antioxidant components, including carotenoids and tocopherols, this herbal plant is deserving attention as a source of dietary fiber. Patients consume wheatgrass during cancer treatment as an adjunct to reduce toxicity associated with drugs and chemotherapy and ultimately improve long-term outcomes. Studies have proved that wheatgrass helps treat pancreatic cancer, lung cancer, and breast cancer. So, the multi-targeted herbal drug—wheatgrass—is used as an adjunct therapy alongside conventional medicine to treat cancer and other diseases. A promising therapeutic nutraceutical for avoiding lifestyle disorders is wheatgrass.

Keyword: drugs, nutraceutical, wheatgrass, medicine

Introduction

Herbal or alternative" medicine is gaining popularity and scientific attributes regarding wheatgrass as a "functional food" is becoming more available and popular as a research topic.

Wheat grass is the mature shoot of *Triticum aestivum* Linn. belonging to the family Gramineae. *Triticum* is a genus of annual and biennial grasses, yielding various types of wheat, native to south west asia (<http://informahealthcare.com>). Common or bread wheat, is widely cultivated almost all over the world. Generally, 15-20 species are recognized of which, 8 have been reported to occur in India. Wheat grass is cost efficient and a source to provide all kinds of nutrients like vitamins, proteins, minerals, antioxidants and medicinal benefits for a healthy and rejuvenating body. Wheat grass has high concentration of chlorophyll, minerals (calcium, potassium, iron, magnesium, sodium and sulphur), 17 forms of amino acids vitamins (A, B, C, E and K) and active enzymes (Lee et al; 2003). It stimulates metabolism and also restores alkalinity to the blood. It is the chlorophyll content in wheat grass that detoxifies the body and strengthens immunity. The three most important effects of wheat grass on human body are blood purification, liver detoxification and colon cleansing. The consumption of wheatgrass in the Western world began in the 1930's as a result of the experiments conducted by Charles Schnabel, a food scientist who experimented with various mixtures of grain and feed and found that chickens fed on mixtures that contained a high proportion of wheat grass had grown better and were healthier. Further research and development continued which had contributed a substantial product to the food supplements industry (Singh et al ;2012).

2. History:

Wheat Grass Juice (WGJ) is an extract squeezed from the mature sprouts of wheat seeds (*T. aestivum*). Wheat grass can be traced back in history over 5000 years in ancient Egypt and perhaps even early in Mesopotamian civilization. It is reported that ancient Egyptians found sacred the young leafy blades of wheat and freeze them for positive effect on their health and vitality. The consumption of wheat grass in western world began in the 1930's as a result of the experiments conducted by Charles Schnabel an agricultural chemist on his hens using wheatgrass to nurse them back to health. He found that when supplemented his ill hen's diets with wheatgrass they doubled their egg production. Schnabel also produced dried and powdered wheatgrass for him and his family to supplement their diets.

The use of WGJ for therapeutic purposes was developed and popularized by Dr. Ann Wigmore, as part of her herbal therapeutic nutritional approach. Wigmore, believed that wheat grass, as a part of a raw food diet, would cleanse the body of toxins while providing a proper balance of

nutrients as a whole food. The use of wheatgrass, particularly its fresh juice became popular again in the 1970s, through Ann Wigmore's „The Wheatgrass Book“ which later on became somewhat of a gospel amongst health supplement fanatics. Ann Wigmore also established the famous Hippocrates Centre treating thousands of clients with herbal grasses and wheatgrass juice (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/wheatgrass>). Fig.1 & 2. In Asia and Europe wheat grass based products are consumed in the form of juices, powders and extracts for the healthy growth of human body. Wheat grass juice is nature's finest medicine. Two ounces of wheat grass juice has the nutritional equivalence of five pounds of the best raw organic vegetables. It is overflowing with vitamins, amino acids, liver enzymes and chlorophyll. It contains 98 of 102 earth elements found in soil, including phosphorous, calcium, iron, magnesium and potassium as well as essential enzymes and 19 amino acids. It has twice vitamin A as in carrots and is higher in vitamin C than oranges (Meyrowitz, 1992). It contains the full spectrum of complete proteins which is in the form of simple polypeptides, a short chain of amino acids that the body absorbs more efficiently in the blood stream. In order to develop a holistic approach for the treatment of chronic diseases, scientists and clinicians world over are now a day's conducting extensive studies to evaluate the efficacy of wheat grass (in the form of powder or juice) and also for the better understanding of therapeutic potential of this medicinal grass (Rajesh et al ; 2011).

2.1 Green Blood Therapy

Green Blood Therapy is the use of Wheat Grass Juice (WGJ) to cure multiple diseases. Wheat grass is called as the green blood. The name “green blood” of wheat grass is attributable to its high chlorophyll content which accounts for about 70% of its total chemical constituents, (The medicinal properties and values of wheatgrass, 2012), (Sweti et al. 2005).

2.2 Nutritional Value

Wheatgrass juice is a rich source of Vitamins A, C, E and B complex, including B12. It contains a multitude of minerals such as calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, alkaline earth metals, potassium, zinc, boron and molybdenum. The various enzymes responsible for its pharmacological actions are protease, amylase, lipase, cytochrome oxidase, transhydrogenase and super oxide dismutase (SOD). The other notable feature of wheatgrass is its high proportion of amino acids such as aspartic acid, glutamic acid, arginine, alanine and serine. It also has a high content of bioflavonoids like apigenin, quercetin and luteolin. All of these enzymes

contribute to its antioxidant activity. Other compounds present, which make this grass therapeutically effective, are the indole compounds, choline and laetrile (amygdalin) (Sweti et al.,2005).

2.3 Wheat Grass Cultivation and Its Parameters

Wheat grass can be cultivated in outdoors, but is commonly grown in indoors on trays filled with potting mix for 15 days. As the leaves grow, they eventually split. At this so called “jointing stage” point the blades can be snipped off, allowing for a second round of leaves to grow. Wheat grass was successfully grown in growth chambers and in field conditions at temperature of 18 to 26 0C and a relative humidity of 40 to 50% was found to be suitable for the growth of wheat grass (Ravi, Pharma Tutor p no: 45).

2.4 Treatment for Multiple Diseases

Wheat grass therapy is recommended for patients suffering from chronic diseases like Asthma,Atherosclerosis, Parkinson’s disease, Joint pains, Constipation, Hypertension, Diabetes, Insomnia, Bronchitis, Sterility, Haemorrhage, Obesity and Flatulence. It is also useful in the treatment of Cancer.

2.1 Vitamins

Vitamin A: It enhances the skin luster and provides glow to the outer skin and makes it disease free.

Vitamin B: It aids in digestion. It is helpful in the treatment of digestive disorders, mental depression, insomnia, premature aging and anorexia.

Vitamin C: It is helpful for recovering from sickness (including the common cold) and preventing

disease such as scurvy. It is a vital substance for healthy gums and teeth and maintenance of bones (Hemilia ,1992)

Vitamin E: It dilates the capillaries and enables free flow of blood. It prevents abortion, diabetes, cancer, heart disorders and dysmenorrhoeal etc. This antioxidant and fertility vitamin is also a protector of the heart (Andrew et al., 2000).

Vitamin K and B-complex vitamins: Wheatgrass is also a source of vitamin B-17, also known as amygdaline, which some studies suggest can help ward off cancer.

In addition to these vitamins, wheatgrass contains 17 amino acids and 92 different minerals the human body uses and needs. The nutrients in wheatgrass are also said to assist in fighting cancer and repairing cellular damage of the lungs.

2.2 Msm

MSM is a sulphur bearing molecule found in all living organisms which get destroyed in processed

food. It helps our Body to use vitamins, helps to reduce allergies, helps detoxify the body and increase oxygen and takes out inflammation.

2.3 Proteins and Amino Acids

Proteins are essential for muscular strength and physical elegance. Plasmas, hormones and antibodies are obtained through proteins. Amino acids aid digestion, blood formation and provide potency to the heart.

2.4 Enzymes

Enzymes are the digestive element helpful for dyspepsia, digestion, building a healthy body and counteract premature aging.

2.5 Minerals

Iron: It is helpful in pregnancy, for excessive sweating, pale complexion, laziness, lethargy, and insomnia. Inorganic iron is often constipating, but the iron salts in wheatgrass have no side effects.

Calcium: Calcium is the prime instigator of vital activity. It strengthens the bones; it restores an alkaline environment in the body for the children and vitality for old. It is helpful in the treatment of diseases like haemorrhage, distension of body, slow movements, coldness and varicose veins etc.

Potassium: Helpful for the radiance and luster of youth, hypertension, dementia, palpitation, tiredness, Suicidal instincts and depression. Potassium, called the youth mineral by some nutritionists, helps to maintain a smooth mineral balance and balanced body weight.

Zinc: Helpful in the prostate gland disorders and nourishes hair. Sodium: Sodium regulates the extra cellular fluid volume. It also regulates the acid-base equilibrium and maintains proper water balance in the body.

Magnesium: Magnesium is important for good muscle function and for bowel health, as it aids eliminative functions.

2.6 Chlorophyll

Chlorophyll the most important element of wheat grass is contained in the cells called chloroplasts. The chemical formation of wheat grass juice has a striking similarity with the chemical formation of human blood (Chenomorsky 1988). The only difference is that the central element in chlorophyll is magnesium and in haemoglobin it is iron. Wheat grass is high in oxygen like all green plants that contain chlorophyll. The molecular structure of chlorophyll in wheat grass and haemoglobin in the human body is similar and because of this wheat grass is called „GREEN BLOOD“. The pH factor of human blood is 7.4. The pH factor of the wheat grass juice is also 7.4 which may be the reason why WGJ is quickly absorbed in the blood. Chlorophyll present in wheat grass can protect us from carcinogens; it strengthens the cells. It is anti – bacterial and can be used inside and outside the bodies as a healer (Wigmore, 1985). Chlorophyll neutralize toxins in the body and improve blood sugar problems.

3. Therapeutic Benefits of Wheat Grass Juice:

Wheat grass juice

Wheatgrass juice is nothing but crude chlorophyll which can be taken orally and as a colon implant without toxic side effects. Wheatgrass is high in oxygen like all green plants that contain chlorophyll. Chlorophyll is anti-bacterial and can be used inside and outside the body as a healer. Chlorophyll (wheatgrass) rebuilds the bloodstream. Wheatgrass juice is a superior detoxification agent compared to carrot juice and other fruits and vegetables. Studies report that 15 pounds of wheatgrass is equivalent to about 350 pounds of carrot, lettuce, celery and so forth (Sean, 2006). Chlorophyll neutralizes toxins in the body. Chlorophyll improves blood sugar problem. A small amount of wheatgrass juice in the human diet prevents tooth decay. Drinking wheatgrass juice is good for skin problems such as eczema and psoriasis. It keeps the hair from greying and improves digestion. It prevents constipation. Chlorophyll is called as 'concentrated sun power'. Chlorophyll increases the function of the heart, the vascular system, the intestines, the uterus and the lungs. Chlorophyll (wheatgrass) is a natural body cleanser, re-builder and neutralizer of toxins. Wheatgrass juice is good for blood disorders of all kinds.

4. Polypharmacological Effects Of WGJ.

4.1 Diseases Related to Blood And Blood Circulation System

Included among this category are anaemia, high blood pressure, atherosclerosis, internal haemorrhage, clotting and the like. Regular intake of the wheat grass juice works wonders

especially in the case of anaemia for which no other therapy has such quick cure. For this an intake of 200 ml juice twice a day is recommended.

4.1.1 Deficiency of Haemoglobin

Wheat grass juice is termed as a substitute for natural red blood cells. Wheat Grass possesses all the compositions that Haemoglobin possesses. It is also known as Green Blood because of its close structural similarity to Haemoglobin. Wheat Grass contains many nutritious and prophylactic ingredients.

4.1.2 Increase of Uric Acid in Blood

The increase of uric acid in the blood causes complications such as swelling of the body, digestion

trouble, insomnia, etc. This can also be cured using WGJ.

4.2 Diseases Related to The Respiratory System

Common cold, asthma, bronchitis and all the related diseases get cured with the regular regimen of this wheat grass juice therapy. Common cold generally disappears within a couple of days. Asthma is a dreadfully stubborn disease responding to almost all given therapy. But wheat grass juice taken twice a day creates wonders in this case also.

4.3 Digestive diseases

Wheat grass therapy is most effective in the case of digestive disorders. Constipation, indigestion, flatulence, nausea, vomiting, acidity, ulcers in the stomach and intestines are some of the prominent diseases. It is an excellent laxative in the severity of rectal bleeding. No serious side effects were found. Grass juice appeared effective and safe as a single or as added support to treat active ulcerative colitis. This enema is very helpful in disorders of the colon, mucous, ulcerative colitis and chronic constipation.

4.4 Teeth and Gum Related Diseases

4.4.1 Tooth Disorders

Wheat is valuable in the prevention and cure of pyorrhoea. It takes time to eat wheat and as it is generally taken with other foods, it compels the chewing of other foods also. Wheat grass juice

Pepper:

Botany Aspect

Classification of the pepper plant [6]:

Kingdom : Plantae (Plant)

Subkingdom : Tracheobionata

Super divisi : Spermatophyta (Seed plant)

Divisi : Magnoliopsida (Two pieces/dicotyledon)

Kelas : Magnoliidae

Sub-kelas : Monocotyledonae

Ordo : Piperales

Famili : Piperaceae (the Betel Tribe)

Genus : Piper

Spesies : Piper nigrum L.

Pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.) is an extensively used spice, which has a characteristic flavor and pungency. The properties of spices such as flavor, color, pungency, etc., vary among cultivars and varieties. It is in this context that pepper cultivars namely, Panniyur 1, Balankotta, Panniyur 5 and one commercial sample were examined for flavor and odor profile using sensory, gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS) and electronic nose (E-nose) analyses. The flavor profile of pepper powder dispersed in cornstarch gruel clearly differentiated Balankotta samples

from the other three samples; green mango-like, turmeric-like and earthy notes were higher in Balankotta samples, while the other samples had higher scores for pepper-like, pungent, spicy and lingering herbaceous. The flavor profile of the essential oils of pepper samples showed a higher intensity of pepper-like note in Panniyur 1, Panniyur 5 and commercial sample, and turmeric-like and green mango-like characterized Bal- ankotta. The odor profile of the essential oils further supported the flavor profile data. Orthonasal olfaction (odor profile) provided more descriptive odor char- acteristics for pepper powder than pepper essential oil. The orthonasal and retronasal olfaction (flavor profile) showed an opposite trend when the flavor profile of pepper essential oil samples was carried out in a starch-based carrier; retronasal olfaction was more effective than the orthonasal. GC, GC–MS analy- sis and E-nose aroma pattern complemented the sensory flavor profiling results.

The GC–MS of Balankotta pepper samples was different from Panniyur 1, Pan- niyur 5 and the commercial sample, showing higher content of p-cymene. The E-nose pattern matching further supported the sensory and instrumental data.

Black pepper, known as the king of spices, is the most popular and most widely used spice in the world. It is extensively used for flavoring and pre- serving processed foods and has medicinal properties. Western coastal regions of south peninsular India is the traditional home of pepper. In India, pepper is cultivated in an area of around 181,500 hectares with an annual production of 60–80,000 tons, which was reported by Ravindran and Johny (2000). The cultivars of black pepper have originated from the wild types; more than hundreds of cultivars are known and a few of them are popular (Ravindran 2000). Gopalkrishnan et al. (1993) described the odor evaluation for Panniyur 1, Panniyur 2, Panniyur 3 and Panniyur 4 of pepper cultivars. They depicted the profile on a 4-point category scale and subjected the oils to ranking tests. The aromagram developed by these authors has the desirable odors of pepper in the upper quadrant and the undesirable odors in the lower quadrant depict- ing the quality of pepper samples. The quality of black pepper is as important as yield and depends on the content of piperine and essential oil. The components of pepper contributing to its value as a food additive are the essential oil for aroma and alkaloid compounds for pungency. The characteristics of pepper alkaloids and the chemistry of the volatile oil were reported by Govindarajan (1977). The author reported that sensory evaluation with trained panels and reference standards is the only technique

available for the evaluation of the degree of superiority of the aroma quality of pepper. More than 80 components have been reported in pepper essential oil. Lewis et al. (1969) studied 17 cultivars from Kerala (India) and found that the oil content ranged from 2.4 to 3.8%. Russel and Else (1973) found a significant difference in the oil content and chemical composition of different varieties of black pepper. Richard et al. (1971) analyzed the pepper samples from Lampong and Sarawak. Pangborn et al. (1970) studied the sensory evaluation of Malabar pepper oil after column chromatographic fractionation and indicated that the early fractions were pepper-like and floral and the late fractions were pepper-like and woody. An aroma model for pepper was developed based on the quantification of 19 odorants, and the calculation of their odor activity values was studied by Jagella and Grosch (1999). Narasimhan et al. (1992) conducted studies on the quality of powdered black pepper during storage by gas chromatography (GC) analysis and sensory analysis. Gopalkrishnan et al. (1993) depicted the odor profile of pepper samples on a 4-point category scale and subjected the oil to ranking tests. However, descriptive odor and flavor analysis by sensory methods are lacking. Peryam and Swarty (1951) demonstrated by consumer-type preference test that pepper was of considerable significance for enhancing the flavor quality of different foods. The authors found significant differences among genuine pepper, extracts and artificial pepper by the paired comparison technique. Aroma is an integrated response to a mixture of components and thresholds of perception. Reports were available on the effect of different dispersal media on the

aroma of the oil or fractions of the oil (Pangborn et al. 1970). Despite poor dispersal in water, thin medium was found to be the best for reflecting quality. The “musty” note was accentuated in the salt medium (Govindarajan 1977). These studies emphasized the importance of selecting a suitable medium for sensory evaluation trials. Electronic nose (E-nose) pattern matching was carried out for discriminating the aroma of pepper cultivars. E-nose, like the human nose, makes a global analysis of vapor emitted from a sample and performs a classification process by comparing the samples with a database. It performs a quick assessment of aroma quality and is being used by the food industry to carry out quality control and product development. E-nose is defined as an instrument that comprises an array of electronic chemical sensors, appropriate pattern recognition system, capable of recognizing simple and complex odors. E-nose is a tool that complements the sensory and instrumental data of flavors and aroma of foods. E-nose testing was used for analyzing coffee aroma and instant coffee powder of different origins

(Gretsch et al. 1998) and quality of tea (Lucas et al. 1998). Madsen and Grypa (2000) used E-nose to determine the origin of spices and compare formulae components in the system. Vanilla flavor evaluation by sensory and E-nose techniques was reported by Hariom et al. (2006). Korel et al. (2002) carried out on using E-nose to discriminate ground red pepper samples by headspace volatiles. This study showed that E-nose was able to group ground red pepper having different capsaicin, dihydrocapsaicin and total capsaicinoids level, using the discriminant function analysis as a pattern recognition technique. E-nose is used by an appropriated pattern recognition technique to identify the odor through comparison with previously obtained measurements of known samples (Barnett 1999; Strike et al. 1999). In this context, quality evaluation through 500 (B.S. Mamatha et al).

Black pepper spices have many benefits in life. The most commonly used service is as a spice in the kitchen because it has a distinctive taste. Black pepper is one of the oldest spices and is most widely used for cooking and in the health sector, namely traditional medicine called the "king of spices." The data collection was sourced from the internet, such as Google Scholar, Researchgate, Science direct, books on black pepper, and trusted journal publishers from 2000-2020. Traditional medicine uses plants that exist in nature, such as roots, stems, branches, leaves, flowers, and fruits that are easier to obtain. Besides not having side effects, they can also be used for a long time. The main content of piperine and essential oil from black pepper has many pharmacological effects, including an antioxidant, antifungal, antimicrobial, antiepileptic, increases libido, anti-diarrhea and others. Based on this, a lot of research has been done on black pepper's chemical content and its pharmacological effects. Spices have a definition of plants used to improve the taste of food, including the skin, flowers, fruit, roots, leaves, rhizomes, seeds, tubers, and other plant parts. Spices are aromatic or intensely flavored parts of plants used in small quantities in foods as preservatives or flavoring in cooking [1]. Indonesia is a country that has abundant spices, one of which is pepper. There are two types of pepper, namely black pepper and white pepper. Black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.) is such a useful medicinal plant that black pepper is called the "king of spices" [2]. Black pepper is used throughout the world for various types of dishes. Black pepper is also used in medicine for multiple types of diseases since centuries ago. Black pepper is useful in treatment, preservatives, and flavorings [3], the cosmetic industry, the perfume industry and is widely used as a medicinal ingredient, both in a single form and in mixed conditions with other components [4]. In Indonesia, pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.) is

used as an antimicrobial, antihypertensive, anti-plasma, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective and antioxidant [2].

Black pepper used for generations (empirically) has long been known in Indonesian [5]. Therefore, the authors are interested in reviewing black pepper, both from its botanical aspects, chemical content, and the pharmacological activity of black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.).

The pepper plant's lateral roots are filamentous at the bottom of the stem and are the taproot. The number of pepper roots is 10-20, with a length of 3-4 meters. Pepper roots can penetrate the soil to a depth of 1-2 meters. The adhesive roots that grow from the stem's knuckles on the ground are not elongated. Their length is quite limited, ranging from 3-5 cm [8]. The stem of the pepper plant is like a long, cylindrical vine and knuckles. Young stems are green, while old stems are woody with a diameter of 4-6 cm. The knuckle can reach 5- 12 cm in length. The pepper plant is a dimorphic plant with two main types of vines, namely climbing tendrils and fruit tendrils. The climbing tendrils have nodes with knuckles that form long, sticky roots that do not have the potential to bear fruit. The fruit tendrils (branches) have a sympodial branching system and grow horizontally (plagiotope). The tendrils of the fruit do not have a root attached to the knuckles. Fruit tendrils are phototropic positive, while climbing tendrils are phototropic negative. In addition to these two types of tendrils, pepper plants are also known as hanging tendrils and soil tendrils. Hanging tendrils are tendrils that grow depending on the canopy surface, while soil tendrils grow along the surface of the soil. Both of them have relatively long knuckles. The stems have more diameter, the leaves are narrower, and do not have attached roots. Anatomically hanging tendrils and soil tendrils come from climbing tendrils. Both are inferior tendrils and so are usually removed by trimming [8]. Pepper leaves are round like eggs, asymmetrical in shape with a tapered tip, sitting single leaves, growing alternately on each stem knuckle. The length of the petiole ranges from 1.8-2.6 cm, the base of the leaves is blunt and notched, the tips of the leaves are tapered, the shape of the leaves varies from oval to heart-shaped (*cordatus*). The width ranges from 5-10 cm and 10-19 cm long. The leaf bones consist of the mother bone (rib) and the branch bones (lateral nerves) curved in 3-4 pairs [8]. The pepper plant has panicle-shaped flowers, about 3-25 cm long, unbranched, single-axis where more than 150 small flowers grow per bunch and grow opposite the branches' leaves. The pepper flower is a compound flower. The color is light greenish-yellow. The panicles hang down in varying lengths. There are pepper

flowers that flower only females, only male flowers, or hermaphrodite (bisexual). Single-celled female genitals consist of 1 ovule. Three hundred five stigmas surround the ovary. On the left/right of the female genitals, there are 2-4 short stamens, each containing two pockets of essence (theca). Pepper flowers are protogynous. The flower candidates were initially eyes. Towards the flowering period, the sprout grows into a bud covered with a leaf sheath [8]. Pepper fruit is generally round or slightly oval. There are three types of fruit, like ordinary fruit, which is green when ripe and red-orange. Fruits that are not normal are small and dark green and will turn black. Pepper's skin is 1-2 mm thick. The skin is hard on young fruit, on ripe fruit, the soft, juicy skin is red-orange and peels easily. The fruit contains essential oils, oleoresin, and piperine, which have different contents in several varieties [8]. Pepper seeds have a white, brown seed coat and smooth surface with a 3-4 mm diameter. The embryo is located near the seed hole (microfilm). The oil content is found in the seed coat [8]. In some areas, the pepper fruit is known as pedes, saang, sakang, or merica [9]. Pepper grows well in areas with an altitude of 0-500 m above sea level, but it is best at the height of 100 m above sea level. The desired rainfall ranges from 2000-3000 mm per year with two dry months to encourage flowering. Rain and wind that are too heavy will shed a lot of flower stalks and fruit bunches rarely. The best air temperature range is 23-32°C with daytime temperatures of 29°C. The soil of interest is light, loose, well-drained, and fertile. Pepper plants are not commonly grown from seed. The seeds are obtained from ripe fruit, massaged to remove the seeds, washed, and wind-dried. Immediately sow the seeds in sand beds, 3-4 weeks after the seedlings will grow. Seedlings at the age of 2 months can be transferred to the main nursery. One meter-long 7-segment cuttings can be planted directly in the garden, while short cuttings, 1-3 segments need to be seeded first. One book cuttings (one leaf) sown on a sand bed, after sprouting within 1-2 months it can be transferred to a plastic bag. Seedlings are kept under the roof for about 3-4 months, reaching a length of 7 sections, ready for planting into the garden [10].

CONCLUSION:

To conclude, wheatgrass seems to be a very promising herbal drug and extensive research work is needed in order to explore its therapeutic application in various diseases. Wheatgrass juice generally contains no harmful substances with the exception of a possible allergic reaction. Wheatgrass is known to help minimize fatigue, improve sleep, increase strength, naturally

regulate blood pressure and blood sugar, support weight loss, improve digestion and elimination, support healthy skin, teeth, eyes, muscles and joints, improve the function of our heart-lungs and reproductive organs, heal ulcers and skin sores, slow cellular aging, improve mental function and is beneficial in arthritis and muscle cramping. It is proven to be beneficial under various conditions, such as anaemia, diabetes, cancer, eczema, constipation, kidney swelling, and common cold. Thus, it should be made part of daily dietary intake in order to explore its maximum benefits.

REFERENCE:

- 1) Asokh, S.A. (2011). Phytochemical and pharmacological screening of wheat grass juice (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Internat. J. Pharmaceut. Sci. Rev. & Res.*, 9: 159-164.
- 2) Bar-Sela, G., Cohen, M., Ben-Arye, E. and Epelbaum, R. (2015). The medical use of wheatgrass: Review of the gap between basic and clinical applications. *Mini-Rev. Medicinal Chem.*, 15 (12) : 1002-1010.
- 3) Dutta, A.K. and Raja, W. (2016). Wheat grass- A perfect food and its anti-microbial properties from the different solvent extract. *World J. Pharm. & Pharmac. Sci.*, 5(9): 1818-1828.
- 4) Ferruzzia, Mario G. and Joshua, Blakesleeb (2007). Digestion, absorption, and cancer preventative activity of dietary chlorophyll derivatives. *Nutr. Res.*, 27 (1): 1–12.
- 5) Gore, R.D., Palaskar, S.J. and Bartake, A.R. (2017). Wheatgrass: Green blood can help to fight cancer. *J. Clinical & Diagnostic Res.*, 11(6): 40–42.
- 6) Kulkarni, S., Tilak, J., Acharya, R., Rajurkar, N., Devasagayam, T. and Reddy, A. (2006). Evaluation of the antioxidant activity of wheatgrass (*Triticum aestivum* L.) as a function of growth under different conditions. *Phytotherapy Res.*, 20: 218-227.
- 7) Marawaha, R.K., Bansal, D., Kaur, S. and Trehan, A. (2004). Wheat grass juice reduces transfusion requirement in patients with thalassemia major: a pilot study. *Indian Pediatr.*, 41(7):716-720.
- 8) Mathur, S., Mathur, R. and Kohli, G.K. (2017). Therapeutic use of wheat grass juice for the treatment of anemia in young women of Ajmer city (Rajasthan, India). *Internat. J. Nutr. Sci.*, 2(1): 1014.
- 9) Melina, Vesanto M.S., Davis, R.D. and Brenda, R.D. (2003). The new becoming vegetarian. page 186-187. *Healthy Living Publications*. Mogra, R. and Rathi, P. (2013). Health benefits of wheat grass – A wonder food. *Internat. J. Food & Nutr. Sci.*, 2 (4):10-13.
- 10) Shakya, G., Randhi, P.K., Pajaniradje, S. and Rajagopalan, R. (2016). Hypoglycaemic role of wheatgrass and its effect on carbohydrate metabolic enzymes in type II diabetic.